

MANIFESTATIONS, CAUSES AND DYNAMICS OF RURAL POVERTY IN MIZORAM

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Abstract

Poverty is a major challenge to social work at multilevel. In India poverty has roots in its exclusionary traditional social structure and a predominant majority of the poor belong the scheduled castes and tribes. The present paper attempts to understand the dynamics of tribal poverty in rural Mizoram from the points of views of social policy and social work. The paper is based on the primary data collected through field survey and in-depth interviews. The study reveals that poverty is perceived by people as multidimensional phenomenon viz., physical, social and economic and they see it as a result of accidental or personal factors rather than rooted in the social and economic structure where they are embedded in. Yet the life experience of poor depicted in the case studies indicate that rural poverty in Mizoram is rooted in the demographic social and economic structure of the society. Poverty is here too transmitted over generations and those who suffer due to poverty are migrants, aged and widows and the families headed by them. Unfortunately for many poor neither the governmental nor non-governmental support readily available. In the light of the results of the study, the need for generalist social work intervention with the migrants, female headed households and aged is emphasized. Further, there is an urgent need for advocating better implementation of centrally sponsored social security measures.

The present paper tries to identify the manifestations and causes of poverty in Mizo villages from the perception of the people and understand the dynamics of poverty from their lived experiences. Poverty is the fundamental challenge to social development in India. Poverty in India is a complex multi dimensional socio-economic phenomenon. It is hunger, lack of shelter and is being sick and not being able to see a doctor. Poverty is also powerlessness, lack of representation and freedom. In Northeast India a majority of the people are below the poverty line. These poor people belong to landless, agricultural labour and petty artisan classes. As regards the magnitude of poverty in Mizoram, almost one half of the

households in Mizoram are poor¹. It was also found that only the Aizawl district has lower proportion of below poverty line (BPL) households than the over all proportion of households of BPL in the state. The highest incidence of poverty was observed in Lawngtlai district where more than 71 percent of households live below poverty line. Further in the districts of Lunglei (65.06%), Mamit (62.89%), and Serchhip (62.91%) more than two thirds of their households below poverty line (see table

Methodology

The design of the study is descriptive in nature. The study is based on field survey with a structured interview schedule. Also a few case studies were used to understand the dynamics of rural poverty. The household survey was conducted in a village located on the northern part of Aizawl District and is under the Tlangnuam Rural Development Block. A disproportionate stratified random sampling procedure was adopted in the present study. The list of the heads of the households of the village was obtained from the president. Three categories were identified viz., non-poor, poor (BPL) and extremely poor (AAY). Sixty (60) households from poor, extremely poor and non-poor (20 each) were selected using simple random sampling with lottery method. A structured interview schedule was used for collecting the primary data. The interview schedule covers the broad areas of demographic, social, economic information. To analyse the data apart from cross tabulation, simple averages and proportions, one way analysis of variance and Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation were used.

Manifestations of Poverty

The concept of manifestations of poverty can be traced back to Copenhagen declaration 1995. The manifestations of poverty may vary society to society. Hence, to identify the manifestations of poverty in Mizoram a question posed to the respondent was that what you mean by poverty? The meanings given by people were grouped into a limited number of manifestations (see table 2). The manifestations of poverty in Mizoram observed were inadequate income, inability to treat disease, homelessness, inadequate food, inadequate clothing, illiteracy, and lack of respect in the community. All these manifestations were agreed upon by a vast majority of the respondents of all the three classes extremely poor, poor and non-poor alike.

Inadequate Income, Inability to treat Decease, and Homelessness were three predominant manifestations reported by the respondents. 95 per cent of the extremely poor, all the poor and more than 85 per cent of the non-poor respondents reported these as the manifestations of poverty. In other words to them poverty means inadequate income, inability to treat decease, and homelessness.

Inadequate Food and Inadequate Clothing as manifestations were reported by more than four fifth of the respondents as a whole while more than two thirds of the poor reported illiteracy and lack of respect in the community as the manifestations of poverty. Thus poverty is not only inability to fulfill the basic physiological needs like food, clothing, health, education but also social i.e. lack of respect in the community and people's understanding of poverty is multidimensional interrelated issues and concerns in the human wellbeing.

Causes of Poverty

The next question is why of poverty. The question why there is poverty in the society or in the family was posed to the respondents. The reported causes were meaningfully grouped into 14 viz., laziness, accident, ill health and disability, inherited from parents, death of bread winner, lack of marketing facilities, illiteracy, ill health disability and handicap, discrimination in development programmes, how income, unemployment, misfortune fate or God, lack of resources, extravagant spending, drug addiction and alcoholism, marital breakdown, and insurgency (see table 3).

Accidents, ill health, disability or death, laziness, inherited from parents were the three predominant causes of poverty in the perception of the respondents. Nearly half of the respondents perceived accident, ill health, disability or death of the breadwinner as the major cause of poverty. More than two thirds of the extremely poor (65%), more than two thirds of the poor and non-poor respondents perceived this as the cause of poverty. Laziness was considered as the main cause by 35 percent of the respondents as a whole. More than one thirds of the extremely poor and non-poor and more than one fourth of the poor respondents reported laziness as the cause of poverty. Inheritance of poverty from parents was reported by less than one fifth of the respondents as a whole. One fifth of the extremely poor and non-poor perceived inheritance as the cause of poverty while 15 per cent of the poor respondents perceived so.

It is clear that the structural roots of the poverty were not at all perceived by the respondents. This could be traced to the non-stratified nature of tribal social structure of the past. The phenomenon of poverty though observed to be rooted in the demographic, social and economic structures it was seen by the poor themselves as accidental, personal or familial.

Suggestions for Poverty Eradication

Suggestions of the respondents for eradication of poverty were elicited. A number of suggestions were made for this open ended question. The suggestions were meaningfully grouped into eight viz., hard work, government loan, education, employment, improved marketing facilities, fair prices for agricultural products, end of discrimination, single disbursement of loan etc. (see table 4).

Hard work (46.67), government loan (13.33), and employment (11.67) were reportedly the three predominant suggestions of the respondents on the whole. However, there was notable difference in the emphasis of the three classes of respondents viz., extremely poor, poor and the non-poor. Hard work as a means to escape from poverty was suggested by most of the respondents of all the categories. 60 percent of poor, 35 percent of non-poor and 45 percent of extremely poor respondents suggested hard work. 30 percent respondents of extremely poor, 15 percent of non-poor and 10 percent of poor respondents put forth government loan as a solution to poverty. 20 per cent of the extremely poor and 15 per cent of the non-poor suggested increase in employment opportunities while none of the poor reported the same. It is interesting to observe the emphasis of the poor and non-poor alike on hard work rather than on the role of government in eradication of poverty. It seems that people have more faith in personal effort over the state intervention.

Dynamics of Rural Poverty

In the previous sections the manifestations, causes, and solutions from the perspective of people were discussed. The question that arises in this context is how is poverty experienced by poor? This question pertains to the dynamics of rural poverty in Mizoram. In order to understand the dynamics of poverty in Mizo villages a few case studies on the lived experience of the poor and very poor households are attempted.

Case 1: A Landless Household

They were five members with three children and staying in a small congested house. Only one room is shared for kitchen and sitting room, only bedroom is separated by curtain and there is no study room for their children, toilet or attached bathroom. Safe drinking water is not sufficient for them. The head of the family is 37 years old and studied up to third standard, his wife is 32 years old also studied up to third class. His parents were divorced when he was only 8 years old. His mother looked after him along with his two siblings. They have no land for cultivation on their own but they cultivate their neighbour's land and usually cultivate bean, mustard, brinjal, and pumpkin but never use high yielding variety seeds. In addition they also go out as daily wage labour. His wife is having kidney problem and could not work hard. Their eldest son (10 years old) is studying fifth standard and second son who is 8 years studying first standard, in the government school. They never got any support from the government or non-governmental organisations.

Case 2: An Unmarried Aged Woman

She is unmarried and 57 years old. She lives alone in a small room of her brother's house without paying any rent. She lost her parents when she was 22 years old. She had borne the responsibility of looking after her four (4) younger brothers. She does not have any means to earn her livelihood but sometimes her brothers extend financial support. She is very much interested in poultry and piggery, also she is a member of a self-help group. She got a free connection of electricity from Government.

Case 3: A Poor Migrant Household

The head of the family is 28 years old and married to a widow with three children. She is older than him and they have one daughter born to them. Both of them were illiterates and have no land for cultivation, as they were migrants from Champhai district in the year 1997. They cultivate rice and vegetables in their neighbour's land on rent. Their eldest son who is 17 years could not continue his studies due to their poverty, while the second one is studying ninth standard in the free hostel run by widows association of Mizoram. The third one is studying eighth standard at P.G School and the youngest one is studying first standard at Government Primary School. They never got any benefit from the government or from any of the non-governmental organisations.

Case 4: A Young Poor Couple

The head of the family is 30 years old and studied up to 8th standard and his wife is 32 years aged and studied up to 5th standard. Both of them do not have any property inherited from the parents. The head of the family had 5 siblings, among them; one's household is below poverty line. They have one daughter who is 3 years old.

Case 5: An Aged Couple

Both the head of the family and his wife were very old who is 87 years and 83 years old. Their youngest son who is married bears the responsibility of looking after them. Their son who is 21 years old and his wife 27 years were illiterates and depend on daily wage labour and cultivate rice at their own land. They could not fully utilize their land due to shortage of water for irrigation. The most crucial problem they suffer is due to low price of vegetables, which they harvest and sell in the local market.

Case 6: An Aged Bachelor

He is bachelor who is 73 years old and stays alone. He was a migrant from Darlung in the year 1969. They were 8 siblings and only two were survived, all the others were dead during their childhood. Even his sister who survived along with him also died in the year 2002. He has his own house and got a free electricity connection from government. He has land and cultivates lemon. He is too old to work hard. He is keeping poultry at his own house. To feed his broiler he relies on credit and repays when he sells them off. The case studies depict the live shows of poverty as experienced by the poor. Impoverishment of households in Mizoram could be attributed to widowhood or loss of breadwinner, old age, migration and land less-ness. Unfortunately these factors and processes have not been taken into account while implementing poverty eradication schemes or social security scheme by the government authorities. Another noticeable lacunae is that of neglect of poverty eradication work by voluntary organisations

Conclusion

Poverty is a major challenge before the state of Mizoram, which is realising the fruits of peace in terms of socio economic development. Though poverty is perceived by people as multidimensional phenomenon physical, social and economic they see it as caused by accidental or personal factors rather than rooted in the social and economic structure where they are embedded in. Yet the life experience of poor depicted in the case studies

indicate that rural poverty in Mizoram is rooted in the demographic social and economic structure of the society. Poverty is here also transmitted over generations and those who suffer due to poverty are migrants, aged and widows and the families headed by them. Unfortunately for many poor neither the governmental nor non-governmental support readily available.

The study indicates certain policy directions too. Firstly, the government of Mizoram need to instruct the village councils to allot lands to the local migrants because among the poor many are migrants and landless. The respective village councils did not allot them land and a major portion of their income from cultivation goes to the landowners whose land they are cultivating. Secondly, there is an urgent need for better implementation of social security measures for the widows and aged people in Mizoram because these groups are out of safety net. Thirdly, better targeting be emphasised in the implementation of rural development programmes in the state because a considerable number of poor feel that the government neglects them. Fourthly, the civil society especially the prominent cadre based community organisations like Young Mizo Association (YMA), Mizo Upa Pawl (MUP), and Mizo Hmeichhia Insuihkhawm Pawl (MHIP)² may come forward to work for eradication of poverty in the state.

Table 1 Household Poverty in Mizoram

Sl.No	District	Number of Households	Number of BPL Households	Percent
1	Aizawl	66437	21863	32.91
2	Champhai	20118	10256	50.98
3	Mamit	12213	7681	62.89
4	Serchhip	10360	6517	62.91
5	Kolashib	11257	5809	51.60
6	Lunglei	25817	16796	65.06
7	Lawngtlai	14239	10116	71.04
8	Saiha	11190	6667	59.58
9	Total	171631	85705	49.94

Source: Computed from Block level statistics of Department of Economics and statistics Government of Mizoram

Table 2 Perceived Manifestations of Poverty

Sl.No	Manifestation	Extremely Poor n = 20	Poor n = 20	Non Poor n = 20	Total N = 60
1	Inadequate Income	19 (95.00)	20 (100.00)	19 (95.00)	58 (96.67)
2	Inability to treat Decease	19 (95.00)	20 (100.00)	18 (90.00)	57 (95.00)
3	Homelessness	19 (95.00)	20 (100.00)	17 (85.00)	56 (93.33)
4	Inadequate Food	16 (80.00)	17 (85.00)	19 (95.00)	52 (86.67)
5	Inadequate Clothing	17 (85.00)	16 (80.00)	18 (90.00)	51 (85.00)
6	Illiteracy	16 (80.00)	15 (75.00)	13 (65.00)	44 (73.33)
7	Lack of Respect in the Community	14 (70.00)	15 (75.00)	14 (70.00)	43 (71.67)

Source: Computed Figures in parentheses are percentages

Table 3 Perceived Causes of Poverty

Sl.No	Cause	Extremely Poor n = 20	Poor n = 20	Non Poor n = 20	Total N = 60
1	Accident, Ill health, Disability or Death	13 (65.00)	9 (45.00)	7 (35.00)	29 (48.33)
2	Laziness	7 (35.00)	6 (30.00)	8 (40.00)	21 (35.00)
3	Inheritance from Parents	4 (20.00)	3 (15.00)	4 (20.00)	11 (18.33)
4	Lack of Marketing Facilities	0 (0.00)	5 (25.00)	5 (25.00)	10 (16.67)
5	Illiteracy	4 (20.00)	4 (20.00)	1 (5.00)	9 (15.00)
6	Discrimination in Development Programmes	2 (10.00)	0 (0.00)	3 (15.00)	5 (8.33)
7	Low Income	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	4 (20.00)	4 (6.67)
8	Unemployment	0 (0.00)	3 (15.00)	1 (5.00)	4 (6.67)
9	Misfortune Fate or God	2 (10.00)	0 (0.00)	2 (10.00)	4 (6.67)
10	Lack of Resources/ Capital	2 (10.00)	1 (5.00)	1 (5.00)	4 (6.67)
11	Extravagant Spending	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	3 (15.00)	3 (5.00)
12	Drug Addiction and Alcoholism	1 (5.00)	0 (0.00)	2 (10.00)	3 (5.00)
13	Marital Breakdown	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	1 (5.00)	1 (1.67)
14	Insurgency	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	1 (5.00)	1 (1.67)

Source: Computed Figures in parentheses are percentages

Note: Multiple responses were elicited

Table 4 Respondents' Suggestions for Poverty Eradication in Mizoram

SLNo	Suggestion	Extremely Poor n =20	Poor n =20	Non Poor n =20	Total N = 60
1	Hard Work and Determination	9 (45.00)	12 (60.00)	8 (40.00)	29 (48.14)
2	Government Loan	6 (30.00)	8 (10.00)	4 (15.00)	18 (13.33)
3	Increased Employment Opportunities	4 (20.00)	0 (0.00)	3 (15.00)	7 (11.67)
4	Education	3 (15.00)	2 (5.00)	3 (15.00)	8 (6.67)
5	Improved Marketing Facilities	3 (15.00)	1 (5.00)	0 (0.00)	4 (6.67)
6	Fair Prices for Agricultural Products	1 (5.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	1 (1.67)
7	End Discrimination	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	1 (5.00)	1 (1.67)
8	Single Disbursement of Loan	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	1 (5.00)	1 (1.67)

Source: Computed Figures in parentheses are percentages

Note: Multiple responses were elicited

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